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MISTHANASIA: A PRACTICE RESULTING FROM THE STATE'S FAILURE TO GUARANTEE FUNDAMENTAL HUMAN RIGHTS

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ABSTRACT

To present the inconsistencies in Brazil's health system, as well as the incoherence in the application of the Principle of the Reserve of the Possible, pointing out the need for judicial activism in order to rescue the dignity of living and also of dying.